

INTENT RECOGNITION USING DISTILBERT AND LANGUAGE MODELS

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ABSTRACT

Intent classification in Natural Language Processing involves identifying the intention of the user based on their input/interaction with an interface. This can be in a natural usage setting (voice assistants) or an interaction between users, customer service personnel, or agents (in a large organization). This paper aims to study the problem of intent classification using language models (like DistilBERT) and Large Language Models (Phi2 and LLAMA3) on open-source datasets available in banking, travel, small talk, office, etc. This is a challenging problem as there is a need for more available data that spans various domains. Identifying the user's intention is sometimes tricky as the classification changes based on the context (and ambiguity in natural language). Apart from the given intents, the data poses a challenge when a user presents the interface with out-of-scope queries (for which the models aren't trained). We test this on transformer-based approaches like DistilBERT and LLMs (like Phi2 and LLAMA3). We find that DistilBERT, with fewer parameters, trains faster and runs inference faster than LLAMA3 and Phi2 (with PEFT-LoRA). We also find that the results from DistilBERT are much better than those of the language model-based approaches for the Banking-77 and CLINC-150 datasets. These two datasets cover various domains (as mentioned above).

Keywords: Classification, Intent Classification, Language Models, Natural Language Processing, Transformers

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I. INTRODUCTION

Intent classification is a sub-field inside Natural Language Processing that has gained increasing prominence due to e-commerce, e-banking, virtual assistants, etc. The problem of intent classification involves identifying the intent of the interacting user. This has broad implications as this is usually the first point of contact between businesses and users.

Routing the user to the correct department (based on their query) saves time and resources (and increases customer satisfaction). Classifying intents is usually challenging due to limited training data (false positives, false negatives, out-of-scope data). When large organizations deal with hundreds of thousands and millions of customer queries, identifying correct customer intent goes a long way (routing customer queries). An increase of 1 % in precision/recall rates translates to a tremendous increase in customer satisfaction. Apart from identifying and routing customer queries, recognizing out-of-scope queries is a significant concern as they vary widely. Similar customer queries may look different but may have different intent depending on the interaction history (of the customer with an agent). In such cases, longer context window-based LLMs may be preferred over BERT-like models.

Accounting for all possible variations may or may not be possible depending on the application. It may be relatively easy if an organization serves customers with specific services (banking or sales only). Otherwise, it is a significant problem. Identifying customer intent may be challenging due to the underlying complexity of language nuances. The customer may interact with the agent for the same intent in several ways. The queries may be paraphrased in several ways, with which the model may or may not be trained. The out-of-scope queries can also be paraphrased in different ways. It is essential to identify all such queries with high accuracy. With the introduction of Transformer architecture, understanding complex sentences with longer context windows has become increasingly easier. This leads to several improvements in intent classification. When models must be deployed in customer-facing applications, latency is a significant concern. In such use cases, smaller models are preferred over larger models due to lower inference time per query. In this work, we compare DistilBERT (which is a smaller model than BERT) with one small LLM (Microsoft Phi2) and one large LLM (Meta's LLAMA3). For this study, due to the presence of multiple classes in the two datasets (Banking-77 and CLINC-150), we measure micro metrics to compare the overall model performance. We see that DistilBERT still outperforms PEFT finetuned Phi2 and LLAMA3. DistilBERT is preferred over the other two models due to the smaller model size and faster inference time.

II. RELATED WORK

Intent classification existed as a field of Natural Language Processing since the 2000s. It emerged as a field of study to understand user intention while interacting with search and e-commerce websites. Original approaches for intent classification included feature extraction based on word frequency, TF-IDF, and NER to better identify user intent based on different interactions. In 2006, Dai et al. [1] experimented with the handling intention of web users while interacting with search engines. The approach included tracking keyword frequency and composing the feature vectors. Then, an SVM-based approach was applied to classify user intention. During the 2010s, user-generated content increased exponentially due to the onset of mobile devices, e-commerce, and smartphones. This resulted in increased use of images and text to understand user intention. In 2010, Tang et al. [2] experimented with multimodal features (combining text features and visual features from images) to improve visual search and better understand user intention. In 2015, Wang et al. [3] used intent classification to classify tweets into several categories (such as food, travel, career, etc.). In 2016, Figueroa et al. [4] used word-based features with ensemble-based classification algorithms (SVM, Naïve Bayes, etc.) to improve user experience in search by better understanding user intent. In 2019, Pérez-Vera et al. [5] experimented with TF-IDF-based approaches with SVM and Naïve Bayes to classify tweets for intent classification. Kuchlous et al. [6] 2020 explored an approach based on sentence embeddings and N-grams. Other word embedding-based approaches (BERT-like) were explored in [7]. BERT, ROBERTA, SciBERT, and XLNet-based approaches were explored on Citation Sentiment Corpus (CSC) and SciCite databases [8].

A Bi-LSTM model to improve intent classification was proposed by Nguyen et al. [9]. Yuan et al. [10] explored the OCR-based approach to extract text from user-sent images (in interaction with agents). Then, BERT-like (OCR BERT, Visual-BERT) models were used to classify intents. BERT-based approaches were explored in the legal domain in [11]. The models used were LEGAL-BERT and LEGAL-RoBERTA on legal datasets. Weak supervision-based approaches were used for email intent classification in [12]. Few shot intent detection approaches using CG-BERT (Conditional Text Generation-BERT) were explored in [13]. In [14], Roberta and BERT-based classifiers were compared for intent classification on SILICONE datasets. More recently, newer means to perform intent classification have emerged due to the emergence of newer language model-based approaches such as GPT, LLAMA, and CLAUDE. After voice assistants and chatbots were introduced in the later part of the 2010s, intent classification has gained more importance in Natural Language Processing. Identifying In-domain and Out-of-domain intents was explored in [15] using ChatGPT, GPT4, and LLAMA2. This is a significant problem because the models shouldn't respond to customer queries in domains in which chatbots/agents aren't experts.

Arora et al. [16] discussed LLM-based approaches to identify users' out-of-scope intents. More recently, in [17], Shah et al. explored LLM-based approaches to generate valid user intents. We have come a long way from using text-based features (such as word frequencies, keywords, TF-IDF, and Bag-of-Words) to BERT-like features to perform intent classification. More recently, the momentum has also moved towards using LLMs to classify user intents.

The future of intent classification will move toward generating and identifying user intents based on language models in specific domains (in which the LLMs are pre-trained).

III. OUR APPROACH

This section discusses our approach to handling multiple user intents in the given datasets. In this study, we have explored CLINC-150 and BANKING-77 datasets. As the name indicates, CLINC-150 contains 150 user intents. An additional intent includes the out-of-scope intents of several users (bringing the total to 151) in the dataset. Similarly, the BANKING-77 dataset has 76 user intents + 1 out-of-scope intent (a total of 77 intents). We chose these two datasets as they are popular in the intent classification field. The CLINC-150 dataset was introduced in [18]. The Banking-77 dataset was introduced in [19] as a financial intent classification dataset. These two datasets are widely used for intent classification tasks.

The CLINC-150 dataset distribution: The train set contains 100 examples per category (including out-of-scope examples). The test set includes 30 examples per category (except out-of-scope intents) and 1000 out-of-scope intents. The train set contains a total of 15100 examples. The test set consists of a total of 5500 examples. The Banking-77 dataset distribution: The train set includes 10003 examples (with varying intents per category). The test set contains 3080 examples per category (40 examples in each of 77 categories). The Banking-77 dataset is more unbalanced than the CLINC-150 dataset (includes 61-187 examples per intent).

Figure 1: Training and Inference on CLINC-150 and BANKING-77 datasets

For this study, we have focused our efforts on three different intent classification approaches: one BERT-like classifier (DistilBERT), one small LLM classifier (Phi-2), and one large LLM classifier (LLAMA3). For LLAMA3, we used the 8B parameter instruct model. These were trained using PEFT-LORA approaches using the HuggingFace transformers API on an A100 GPU. All three models were trained using PEFT-LoRA fine-tuning [20] for five epochs each with carefully chosen hyper-parameters (learning rate, weight decay), etc. A similar approach was taken in [21]. We chose PEFT-LoRA fine-tuning as it requires relatively less GPU compute to train; instead of updating the entire model, we fine-tune only few trainable parameters with the rest of the model frozen. For the DistilBERT model, we chose the uncased version for simplicity. We use weighted cross entropy to account for unbalanced training examples per category or intent. We follow a similar approach follow. We chose these three models for the sake of comparing these widely different architectures as DistilBERT is lightweight (in terms of GPU compute requirements), Phi-2 is a relatively small LLM but thoroughly efficient, and the LLAMA3 is a large and powerful model. The outline of the training and inference process is highlighted in Figure 1.

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

In this section, we discuss the performance of these three models on CLINC-150 and BANKING-77 datasets. Tables 1 and 2 show the performance of DistilBERT [22], LLAMA3 [23], and Microsoft Phi-2 on the train and test sets, respectively. We can see that training is nearly perfect with precision and recall scores for DistilBERT and LLAMA3. The Phi-2 model is just a little behind at 98%. For the test set, DistilBERT outperforms LLAMA3 and Phi-2. Similarly, in Tables 3 and 4, we see the performance of DistilBERT, Phi2, and LLAMA3 on the train and test sets, respectively. Like Tables 1 and 2, the training performance is good on DistilBERT and LLAMA3 (which comes a close second). However, Phi2 struggles in this case at 89%. For the test set, DistilBERT still comes out on the top.

The LLAMA3 model is better than Phi-2 for the test set on BANKING-77 datasets.

CLINC 150 + OOS			
Model	Precision	Recall	F1
DistilBERT	0.99	0.99	0.99
LLAMA3	0.99	0.99	0.99
Phi2	0.98	0.98	0.98

Table 1: CLINC-150 Train set performance

CLINC 150 + OOS			
Model	Precision	Recall	F1
DistilBERT	0.88	0.86	0.85
LLAMA3	0.81	0.81	0.81
Phi2	0.79	0.79	0.79

Table 2: CLINC-150 Test set performance

BANKING 77 + OOS			
Model	Precision	Recall	F1
DistilBERT	0.99	0.99	0.99
LLAMA3	0.95	0.95	0.95
Phi2	0.89	0.89	0.89

Table 4: BANKING-77 Train set performance

BANKING 77 + OOS			
Model	Precision	Recall	F1
DistilBERT	0.92	0.92	0.92
LLAMA3	0.88	0.88	0.88
Phi2	0.83	0.83	0.83

Table 4: BANKING-77 Test set performance

This outlines the fact that the LLAMA3 and Phi-2 models aren't primarily powerful at intent classification. However, they can show formidable performance when the task involves identifying language complexity and nuances. The DistilBERT model is very good at text-classification (intent classification) tasks and runs faster as well.

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